

北京理工大学

本科生毕业设计（论文）任务书

题目类别： 毕业设计

题目性质： 软件开发

在线租赁系统的设计与实现

Design and implementation of online rental system

学 院： 计算机

专 业： 计算机科学与技术

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北京理工大学本科生毕业设计（论文）

题目内容:

The online rental system, which uses the internet, has a web-based application in which users can look at available items, register, see their profiles, and reserve things. A very sophisticated rental reservation tool, the SAVIO© application, makes handling varied product rentals simpler by combining many forms of reservations and rental settings on a single dashboard.

We will be setting up a web site for each city to serve as a reference for travelers. To streamline the usage of the rental showroom system, instead of having the application just utilize one rental showroom, it acts as a communication channel between customers and the rental showroom owners. To ensure quality, we do not limit the rental showrooms of our website. Let's say your business wants to advertise items on our site. All you have to do is fill out this registration form with your personal information and payment card information, and you're good to go.

The vendor management program is adding some extra functionality to allow suppliers to amend or remove their items. Our customers do not need to register with our site. There are only three steps: search, put orders, and move on. We're responsible for the communication between the client and the provider, and we're in charge of the database. It also has an additional module whereby it takes consumer comments into consideration. There is an additional functionality available via the program called "Relocation Services".

任务要求:

By this project instead of providing products from only one rental show room it provides all products as well as information at one place, this application acting as an interface between user and the rental showroom owners. Thus any rental showroom owner can display their products in our portal by simply register in our site by providing personal information without any restriction. This application provides some additional features to vendor to modify the products.

The purpose of this project is to transport the goods from source to destination in an effective and efficient manner. Rental hub is one stop rental portal. It provides services

such as hiring cars, Apartment, Guest houses, Meeting & Conference halls and Computers. It provides the facility to make online orders and get everything done before you reach destination.

Task we need to do :

System Analysis :

1. Registration
2. Advertise product
3. Data base maintenance
4. Searching and Booking the product
5. Verify Bookings and Intimate to Vendor
6. Authentication

Technical tasks we need to for the development of this project :

1. System design
2. Implementation of project
3. Testing
4. Output screens.

SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS :

Operating System Server: Windows XP or later

Database Server: Microsoft SQL Server-2016

Client: Microsoft Internet Explorer

Tools: Microsoft Visual Studio .Net-2019

User Interface: ASP. Net with C#.Net

Code Behind: VC#.Net

HARDWARE SPECIFICATION:

Processor: Intel Pentium or More

Ram: 512 MB Ram

Hard Disk: PC with 20GB

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指导教师 EXIOM （签字）

2021 年 5 月 25 日

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题目	在线租赁系统的设计与实现		
评阅结果	B 78.0		
<p>评语：</p> <p>选题针对在线租赁系统问题，具有一定的应用价值，论文介绍了相关领域研究现状。</p> <p>论文分析了在线租赁系统的需求，设计完成在线租赁原型系统，能够支持用户登录、查询、查看、更新、删除等功能，并进行了实际测试。</p> <p>论文结构合理，引用规范，设计方案恰当，有一定工作量，过程规范，表明学生具有专业基础知识和综合运用能力，已具备工程实现能力，论文基本达到本科毕业设计对应的毕业要求，同意参加论文答辩。</p>			
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题目	在线租赁系统的设计与实现		
评阅结果	B 75.0		
评语： 选题针对在线租赁问题，具有一定的应用价值，论文分析了在线租赁的需求，设计完成了在线租赁系统，该系统实现了客户、供应商、管理员三大类功能模块，并进行了实际环境测试。论文结构较合理，引用较规范，设计方案恰当，有一定工作量，过程规范，表明学生具有较为扎实的专业基础知识和综合运用能力，已基本具备独立工程实现能力，论文基本达到本科毕业设计对应的毕业要求，同意参加论文答辩。			
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赵刚	讲师	委员	赵刚
杨明	商工	委员	杨明
汤世平	讲师	秘书	汤世平

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1. 系统开发过程中的编码规范是什么？
答：主要是产品的搜索和注册功能。此外，数据维护的功能也很重要。
2. 系统运行过程中有哪些问题？如何处理？
答：主要是服务器上的负载和应用的挂起。采用负载均衡的方法来处理。
3. 是否将你的方法和其它方法进行对比？进行过系统性能测试？
答：主要是进行了系统功能测试。性能测试是对于用户的实际操作进行。

答辩委员会（小组）代表 汤世平（签字）
2021年6月7日

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2021 年 6 月 7 日

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2021 年 6 月 7 日

毕业设计（论文）开始日期 2021年 1月4日

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在线租赁系统的设计与实现

摘要

随着社会的发展，信息网络已经成为时代的主题。网上租赁行业的工作管理过程复杂多样。通过计算机帮助实现网上租赁和相关业务的管理，不仅方便了用户信息的登记、车辆信息的管理、提高了工作效率，而且可以使管理工作变得更加准确、高效、清晰、透明。

本文简要介绍了系统的相关知识和技术，详细介绍了“网上租赁系统”开发的整个过程，包括需求分析、总体设计、模块划分和实现过程。最后，对系统开发过程中遇到的问题进行了分析和总结并提出了解决办法。本系统采用 MVC 设计模式来完成，每个 servlet 用来完成一组相关的业务操作，采用 ASP 网络编程技术，前台采用 Microsoft Visual Studio 开发环境，后台采用 MySQL 数据库作为开发平台，使用 Microsoft SQL Server Management Studio 软件进行数据库管理。

这个应用程序开发的动机是为用户和租赁产品的所有者提供一个平台，以有效和高效的方式进行交流。本篇文章，我们介绍了一个应用程序-网上租赁系统，它可以提供一系列服务，如租赁日常产品，如家具，书籍，汽车，衣服，配件，健身器材，机电一体化等。

基本上这个应用程序可以在孟加拉国和印度使用。但在最近的将来，这种应用可以在其他国家使用。任何城市的人都可以使用这个软件来租用产品。但来自达卡、海得拉巴、艾哈迈达巴德、班格罗尔、加尔各答、钦奈、德里、浦那、孟买的人将得到更多的好处。因为在这些城市我们会有陈列室。所以，人们可以很快得到他们的产品。有时人们有很大的工作压力。这就是为什么他们不能出去买或租一些产品。这个应用程序可以解决孟加拉国的这个问题。人们可以随时从家里订购，我们会把产品送到他们的地址。我已经翻译了我网站的一些内容。我也考虑过关于网站布局，设计，字体大小，和许多其他技术组成部分。所有产品使用方便，质量高，可靠。我保留了成功本地化的这些因素。

关键字：ASP.NET，数据库，Web 服务器，Visual Basic.NET.

Design and implementation of online rental system

Abstract

With the development of society, information network has become the theme of The Times. The work management process in the online rental industry is complex and diverse. Through the computer to help achieve online rental and related business management, not only convenient management of user information and vehicle information, to improve work efficiency, and can make the management work become more accurate, efficient, clear, transparent.

This paper briefly introduces the relevant knowledge and related technologies of the system, and introduces the whole process of the development of the “Online Rental System” in detail. Finally, it analyzes and summarizes the problems and solutions encountered in the process of system development. This system uses MVC design mode to complete, each servlet to complete a group of related business operations, using ASP network programming technology, the foreground using Microsoft Visual Studio development environment, the use of Microsoft SQL Server Management Studio software for database management.

Basically, this application can be used in Bangladesh and India. But in the recent future, this application can be used in other countries. People from any city can use this software to rent products. But people who are from Dhaka, Hyderabad, Ahmedabad, Bangalore, Kolkata, Chennai, Delhi, Pune, Mumbai will get more benefits. Because in these cities we will have a showroom. So, people can get their product very quickly. Sometimes people have a lot of work pressure. That’s why they are not able to go outside to buy or rent some products. This application can solve this problem. People can order anytime from home and we will send the product to their address. I have translated some of my website’s content. I have also considered the website layout, design, font sizes, and numerous other technical components. All the products are easy to use, high-quality, and reliable. I have maintained these factors for successful localization.

Key Words: ASP.NET, Database, web server, Visual Basic.NET

目 录

摘 要	XI
Abstract	XII
Chapter 1 Introduction	
1.1 Outline of the Project	1
1.2 Project Description	1
Chapter 2 Problem Identification	
2.1 Existing Systems	2
2.2 Proposed Systems.....	2
Chapter 3 Analysis of the specific System	
3.1 Software Requirement Specification (SRS)	3
3.2 Requirements for Hardware	9
3.3 Requirements for Software.....	9
Chapter 4 System Design for Online Rental System	
4.1 Component architecture	10
4.2 Flowcharts of Data (DFD)	12
4.3 E-R diagram.....	19
4.4 UML diagram	20
4.5 Module design	23
4.6 Sequence diagram.....	25
4.7 Design of the Database	27
4.8 Data Dictionary	30
Chapter – 5 Implementation of Project.	
5.1 Implementation of vendor.....	33
5.2 Admin	40
5.3 Customer.....	42
Chapter – 6 Testing of the system	
6.1 Evaluation of devices	46
6.2 Example of test cases.....	48

北京理工大学本科生毕业设计（论文）

6.3 Summary.....	52
Chapter – 7 Screens Performance	
7.1 Output Screens	54
7.2 Summary.....	56
Conclusions	57
Renovations in the Future.....	58
References	59
Thanks	61

Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Outline of the Project:

The aim of this project is to safely and effectively transport goods from suppliers to destinations.

The rental center function is a one-stop-shop for all of our rental needs. It provides facilities such as car rentals, home options, restaurants, guest houses, meeting rooms and conventions, audiovisuals, meetings, and device rentals, among others. It allows you to place an order digitally and get everything completed before you arrive at your destination.

1.2 Project Description:

This project would provide a website for a number of cities. Rather than providing goods from a single rental showroom, this program acts as a user interface for consumers and showroom operators. The rental showroom on our website has no restrictions. This ensures that any owner of a Rental Showroom needs to get their items shown on our web; after that, they merely sign up on our site by offering individual details and also charge card or debit card numbers.

This application provides vendors with many unique features that enable them to change or delete their goods. Clients are not required to register on our website. They are simply using our platform to browse for and purchase items. We are in charge of establishing a database and facilitating contact between customers and vendors. It also includes external modules for receiving consumer reviews. This application often includes “relocation facilities,” which is a useful function^[15].

There are a variety of leasing schemes accessible on the internet. However, they no longer show any of their products in the same place. Furthermore, all of them are limited to a single city. That is to say; online car rental services just work with automobiles. Furthermore, the majority of them do not have effective client-distributor contact. There’s also a leasing scheme that’s only available from one seller, which implies the commodity is only available from one rental display room.

Chapter 2 Problem Identification

2.1 Existing Systems

How is it possible to lease anything from a specific city from the comfort of one's own home? How is it possible for an individual to travel to another city but want to rent a product before arriving at his home? As a result, our website is the solution to these questions.

On the internet, there are a plethora of leasing systems to choose from. However, they can not have all of their goods in a single location^[9]. Furthermore, they are all restricted to a single city. That is a car rental system with just a car in an online sale. Many of them don't enable consumers and vendors to communicate effectively. There's also a leasing scheme that's only available from one seller, which implies the commodity is only available from one rental display room.

- They are restricted to a single commodity and a small number of locations.
- Consumers and suppliers are unable to communicate effectively.

2.2 Proposed Systems

The recommended method, also known as the suggested system, is an online framework that can be used by clients from all around the world. More goods from vendors in different fields can be provided by the framework^[12].

Vendors sign up for this framework right away in order to access the system's user interface without having to learn how to use it. By submitting a credit/debit card number, he will cover the cost of advertising his own leased commodity.

The proposed framework will accommodate a wide range of goods for leasing, and this system interface allows vendors to upload photographs of their products into the system. This product picture prompts a customer to communicate with it and receive the information they need about rental properties.

Customers may order rental device items for their own use via the proposed system, which accepts internet orders. The position of the administration is critical in this situation.

Using this method, administrators can relay some commodity reservation details to specific vendors.

Chapter 3: Analysis of the specific Systems

3.1 Software Requirement Specification (SRS)

A general overview

The aim of this project is to use the rent to move materials from sources to destinations in a cost-effective and reliable manner.

Universal Rental Capture is a one-stop-shop for all of your rental needs. It offers auto rental, apartment facilities, restaurants, guest houses, meeting rooms and conventions, audio graphics, group planning, and device rentals, among other things. It allows you to place an order online and finish everything before you arrive at your destination^[8].

The number of parts

Following a thorough review, the following components have been identified as being used in the system:

The following modules are dealt with by the online rental system:

- Registration process
- Advertise the product
- Database maintenance
- Search and order products
- Ensure the vendor's order and information
- Authentication process

Registration of Vendor

The vendor can fill up the registration type by submitting personal information and registering successfully with the website.

a. Requirements:

- Vendor tab

b. Featurealties :

- New suppliers will be developed, among other things.
- Information about the vendor has been included.
- Each vendor is given a one-of-a-kind identifier as well as a password.

c. Inquiries :

- Does username have some sort of account?
- Is there a username that still exists?
- What is the E-mail address for a certain Username?
- Do you know where the vendor is located?

d. Warnings :

- The account was successfully established, according to the fourth warning.
- Login already exists
- Username/password is invalid
- All fields are needed

Market Items: After entering into the supplier's homepage supplier would definitely advertise his products by loading, including item sort by providing enough information about an item such as product id, accessible dates, rent out, etc. and also publish the picture of that item

It contains the following sub-modules:

- a. Update the items.
- b. Remove Items

Update Object: The retailer will update the current product specifics such as rent, accessible days, etc. by bringing in the item id of that item

Remove Object: Supplier can uninstall his goods by entering through the product id of the current item.

a. Requirements

- **Product**

b. Featurealties :

- The connection between vendor tab and items.
- Extending new model Information
- Managing new items, photographs and rent.
- Editing leases and available merchandise.

c. Inquiries :

- How about the number of drugs?
- How many specific products available there?

- What products are present in the showroom?
- How much money does the buyer need to spend to rent a product?
- What kind of product does the buyer choose?

d. Warnings:

- All the sectors are needed.
- The products were used successfully.
- The product identifier is already available.
- It is not appropriate for the end date to come before the beginning date.
- The start date must be no less than the next day.
- The ending date may be later than the beginning date.

Upkeep of the database:

Information provided by the providers, such as object details, personal data, etc, as well as information provided by the user, such as answers and reservation information, is saved in a database by the website manager.

a. Requirements:

- **Bookings**
- **Feedbacks**

b. Featurealties :

- The connection between goods and bookings
- Input which has been provided by users is inserted
- The product is reserved for a certain amount of time by the consumer. These records are added to the database.
- The information about the products is contained in a database.
- The Database contains vendor-specific information.
- The database's information is kept safe.

c. Inquiries:

- How about the number of items is booked?
- What is the good that has been reserved for today??
- What do consumers have to say about it?

d. Warnings :

- All of the sectors are needed.
- The placement of products is effective.
- The retailer is efficiently recorded

Searching and booking the products

The following are the steps for searching for and booking items: After browsing the internet, every user looks for products. After booking the product, he must load the type of his/her booking and submit it to the data source if he finds the right product.

a. Featurealties:

- Search the products
- Book a product
- View the showrooms and product descriptions.

b. Inquiries:

- What exactly are goods in a showroom?
- How much does the item cost?
- Are the items available for scheduling on a certain date?

c. Warnings:

- Both fields must be filled out.
- Item has been successfully booked.

Validate Reservations as well as Intimate to Supplier:

When the user logs in, the Administrator makes sure all previous bookings have been completed. In order to ensure bookings are properly passed through, he must forward all booking information to the Vendors.

Authentication: Authentication is nothing other than ensuring protection for the device. Here every time, you have to get through the device sign-in part^[5]. A page for logging into the website would definitely block UN-accredited users. A consumer needs to provide user IDs and passwords, which are examples of credentials to go through the device. For that device manages data for all consumers. Whenever a person goes through a customer ID and password, it signs in the database for the presence of the user. If the client remains, it should be interacted with as a legal person. Otherwise, the order would return.

Role:

The key position involved in this online rental scheme is

- a. Vendors
- b. Administrator
- c. Customers

The system structure diagram is given below :

Figure 3-1 System structure diagram

The system structure is a complex piece of software known as a Web application, in this case, is in the process of being developed^[17]. The whole product has a large number of elements, such as the user interface, a login screen, an in-app shop, and the servers. To better handle all of these elements, software engineering invented mobile and web application design to identify and organize all the components' relationships and connections such that all of them are neatly packaged in a Web app.

In order to illustrate the design of a web application, we can explain how many of the components mesh together.

In every Web program, you can find two distinct parts: the front end and the back end.

All that a user encounters and communicates within their browser, which we call the front-end, is often referred to as the client-side^[8]. The client-side has two key purposes: it collects data from consumers, and it validates that the data is right. It is written in different variations of HTML, CSS, and JavaScript^[10].

Then, we have the back-end, which is also regarded as the server-side of the app. It is a portion of the system that is not available to end-users; it collects and manipulates details. These backend processes handle HTTP queries, which are simply "fetch" the data (text, photos, files, etc.) requested by the user^[18]. Not all backend programming languages support the frontend; hence, some languages including PHP, Java, Python, JavaScript, and others can be used for backend Web application development. In my case, I have used ASP.NET and C# programming language.

Web application architecture has changed in many ways.

Though there are only two main Web Application Architectures (Server-Side Rendering (SSR) and Client-Side Rendering), all of these architectures are extremely common (CSR)^[16].

Server-Side Rendering:

A request is submitted to the server when you access a website by selecting a URL. The server gets the HTML, CSS, and JavaScript files after the request is finished processing, and then it makes the output of the website^[12]. An additional request will be made if the customer wishes to go to another location on the website.

Client-Side Rendering:

As it comes to Server-Side Rendering (Server-Side Rendering, SSR) and Client-Side Rendering (Client-Side Rendering, CSR), the key distinction being that a single request is sent to the server, and then the skeleton of the software is loaded. In this process, JavaScript is used to dynamically generate content.

Any one of these patterns has both benefits and drawbacks; here is a comprehensive evaluation:

Table 3-1 comprehensive evaluation

	Rendering on the server	Rendering on the client
Pros:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Websites are quick to crawl, making them better for search engine optimization (Search Engine Optimization) • Page load time is much quicker at the beginning. • If you have static information and no dynamic content, this plugin is excellent. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State-of-the-art web design • The website is really fast after the initial load. • This would be ideal for websites.
Cons:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A lot of server traffic. • The page makes at a snail's pace • Reloads with the whole tab. • day-to-day site operations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If you don't apply SEO properly, it can lead to lower SEO. • Loading can take a while. • includes an external library in most situations.

3.2 Requirements for Software:

System software: Windows XP or later

Client-Server Protocol: Microsoft Internet Explorer

Databases(DB) : Microsoft SQL Server-2014

User-Friendly Interface: Asp.NET with Ajax

Instruments: Microsoft Visual Studio .Net-2019

Codes : VC #.Net

3.3 Requirements for Hardware:

Type of the processor: Intel ® Pentium ® Processor / new edition.

Random Access Memory(RAM): 2 GB Ram

Disk space : 500 GB

Chapter 4 System Design for Online Rental System

4.1 Component architecture:

The functional structure diagram of the system is given below:

Figure 4-1 The functional structure of the system

Vendor Services:

The vendor is the owner of a showroom rental that advertises its assets on our website. He is an authorized customer of our website. To promote the commodity, it must access the website by providing the username and password right.

Functionalities of vendor :

- a. The vendor can log in to the system by providing a user Id and password.
 - The vendor can see all the products that have been added or modified by him.

- He can add any new product to the system.
 - The vendor is able to update or modify any product at any time.
 - The vendor can remove the products from the system.
 - During the registration, process the vendor needs to provide his personal information. After completing this step, he will be able to see his profile.
 - The vendor can sign out after finishing his own task.
- b. Another functionality is to complete the registration process. The vendor can register in the system by providing all the necessary information.
- c. If a vendor forgets his own password, then there is another functionality called to forget the password. The vendor can retrieve his password at any time by answering the security question.

Administrator services:

The administrator manages a directory for our website. He is also responsible for ensuring contact with consumers and vendors.

Functionalities for administrator :

- a. **Login:** By providing the admin Id and password admin can access the homepage of the administrator.
- In the login interface, the admin will be able to see all the orders for today.
 - Admin can see all the inquiries provided by the customers and analyze the information.
 - Admin can see the feedbacks and make a change to the system before implementing the software.
 - Admin can sign out at any time.
- b. If the admin forgets his own password, then retrieving the password is also available in the system.

Customer services:

Customers are unregistered consumers. They only enter site search for items if the right product is identified. It basically fills in the order form by supplying a product ID, personal information and sends it to the servers. Customers often have a return by providing comments to the administrator regarding the website.

- The customer doesn't need to log in or register in the system. He can just browse the system and able to see the products in the system.
- If the customer wants to rent any product from a particular city or to buy a particular product, then he can search the products on the website. He will be able to select a specific city or particular product.
- If the customer is satisfied with our service, then he can provide feedback to us.
- An inquiry option is also available there.
- Customers can rent any product from the website without registering to the system. He can just provide all the necessary details and book the product.

The layout of the software framework is based on the technological heart of the software application innovation method as well as is used separately of the creation model and even the implementation area. Architecture is the primary stage in the construction process for every kind of product or engineering framework. The artist has as his aim to create a person's version or picture that is built. The coding and checking necessary to construct and validate the program beginning with three technological design activities; once the device requirements have been identified and tested, the system architecture is. In one expression, "top quality," the value can be established. Design is an ecosystem in which software development fertilizes efficiency. The architecture offers us a machine image that can measure consistency^[6]. The architecture is the only way we can accurately equate user views into products or completed product device programs. The coding style is a structure for all subsequent phases of software application design. We risk designing an unstable device without a solid architecture - which would inevitably be challenging to assess, whose high efficiency will not be examined before the last stage.

Throughout the architecture, complex improvement of knowledge system, software layout, as well as step-by-step information established analyzed and also reported. System architecture should be viewed from the viewpoint of technical managers or programs. From a technological point of view, the architecture comprises four building types, data structure layout, device layout, and proceedings layout.

4.2 Flowcharts of Data (DFD)

We will use the data flow chart as a central tool. From this central component, all the

other parts of the system will be created. This is also used as the main part of the project or system. It describes and analyzes the motion of information as a graphics device. Improvement of the information, via processed, can be rationally as well as independently clarified from the physical element associated with the system^[10]. This is called a rational data flow diagram. The physical data flow diagram reveals tools as well as real data movements between people, divisions as well as workstations.

Building data flow diagram :

Several pragmatic principles are utilized to draw out DFD:

Several guidelines for drawing DFDs are based on rules of thumb.

- One thing the process should provide is a name and number so you can return to it quickly. The names should convey the procedures.
- From top to bottom and from left to right is the flow's course. Data historically moves from the source to the end, however may return to the origin. By using long flow lines, you will show that it comes from a source by drawing a long flow line that leads back to it. A different approach is to make a copy of the source symbol and apply it to a different goal. This appears in the DFD more than once, because it has a short diagonal.
- Once a method is broken down into smaller pieces, they are given numbers.
- When specifying the name of the data store and destination, they will be written in capital letters. The first letter of the work-capitalized word is part of the name of the process or dataflow.

A DFD indicates the minimum amount of data stored in the data store. Both incoming and outgoing data components should be represented in each data store.

Information from questionnaires should provide all the data that goes in and out. In the case of missing interface redundancies and like, interviewees are often used to account for them.

DFD Diagrams:

Context Level DFD Diagrams:

Figure 4-2 Context Level DFD Diagrams

The above figure displays an online rental system background data flow diagram. In this part, an "online rental system" is a procedure (shape) that shows the system to model. It also demonstrates the actors that communicate with the scheme, known external entities. The vendors, customers and administrators are the entities that communicate with the machine. In this case. Data flow (connectors) implies the presence of knowledge sharing between entities and the system between process and external entities.

Data Flow information about the admin:

The first stage of the DFD is as follows:

Figure 4-3 1st Stage of DFD

The above figure indicates level 1 DFD, which is the decomposition (i.e. separate into various components) of the DFD-related online rental scheme. In this chart, I shall present some of the main concepts.

Four processes, an external entity and four data stores are seen in the online rental system data flow diagram illustration. While there is no style directive governing form placement in a data flow chart, we prefer to make it easy to understand processes on the sides of the center, the databases and external entities.

As seen in the illustration, an Admin is requesting an order through the "See order" process. "See order" also gets Order specifics. The "Order details" data store passes information about an order to this process. The outcome is proof of the Administrator's order, which is made.

In a similar way if the admin wants to log in to the system to see all the details; he needs to provide all the necessary information to log in. He needs to make a login request to the “Login” process. From the existing database, the information will be identified. After successful verification admin can successfully log in to the system.

Admin can check queries by making a query request to the “Check inquiries” process. The process checks the existence of query information in the data store. Due to this, the Admin gets the query data Although we've noted that “Check inquiries” creates the question information, the Data Flow Diagram doesn't show this. Our common sense explains how we see the diagram as we see it.

Data Flowing information about the seller:

DFD first stage:

Figure 4-4 1st Level DFD

Additionally, the figure above depicts the DFD stage 1, which depicts the decomposition (i.e. break down) of the “Online renting system” mechanism seen in the sense DFD.

Seven processes, one external entity, and two data stores are identified in the Online Rental System Data Flow Diagram that illustrates the seller's data flows.

Based on the diagram, we know that a Customer can place a request in the registration process. The Registration process receives the request, forwards it to the vendor details data store, and store the updated vendor details in the vendor details data store.

The second part represents the “Login” process. If vendor details exist in the vendor details data store then the “Login process” will make verification and allow the vendor to visit his homepage.

The other processes are called view product, update product, add product, delete the product, and view profile. The methods in the view product and view profile are almost the same. After making the request; The information will be verified in the data store. Only then the vendor can see his product and also his profile.

The methods in updating product, add products, delete product processes are the same. Inventory reports are kept in the Inventory data store after which the order is sent to the data stores.

Data Flowing information about the customer:

DFD first stage:

Figure 4-5 1nd Level DFD Diagrams: (customer)

There are five processes, two external entities, and three data stores involved in this data flow concerning the user.

The diagram confirms that customers may access search information through the "search" process, which is done through accessing the products database. Since common sense tells us that the "Search" function is almost certainly in the software, but the Data Flow Diagram does not explicitly say that. A data flow diagram method may be a function or a group of features.

Customers can book one or more items from the website and place an order. After placing an order the request will be moved to the products data store. If the data store can identify the booking details then the booking details will be shifted to admin. Then admin will confirm the shipment and send the product to the customer. The data flow is indicating the following process. The customer can also provide his valuable feedback and it will be stored in the feedback details database through the "feedback" process.

4.3 E-R Diagram:

The online rental system is a website that helps showroom owners to display their accessible and usable merchandise and vehicles for sale. It is often very helpful to others who search for a range of products. The manager and seller will be the moderator for all purchases on the website to ensure that the process is seamless for all parties (car owner and customer).

The first phase in developing the Online Leasing System is to design the ER diagram which will later function as the foundation when the actual database is created.

We build and illustrate the method of drawing up the car rental system's business partnership diagram.

Let's begin with the ER diagram's symbols used.

The entity is seen in the form of a rectangle. The company will be our online rental system database table later.

The attribute is the oval kind. These are the columns or fields in the online rental system of each seat.

The link is the diamond type. The relationships between individuals are thus determined.

This is generally in the shape of an external key.

When making the ER Diagram, we will obey the 3 fundamental laws.

1. List all bodies. List all bodies.
2. Identify the bond between organizations and
3. Give our organizations significant attributes.

Step 1. We have the following entities in the Online rental system

- Products
- Vendor
- User
- Administrator

The above-described individuals are now being drawn and defined by the rectangular form of the online rental system.

Entity-relationship diagram :

Figure 4-6 Entity-Relationship(ER)

4.4 Unified Modeling Language(UML) Diagram

In our scheme, we have a use case diagram that looks like this:

Figure 4-7 Use case Diagram in our system

Extended Use case Diagram in our system:

Figure 4-8 Extended Use case diagram in our system

This describes how an actor is used, as well as the features it offers.

In addition to illustrating the actor-use case interaction, the actor and use case descriptions often include more information about each actor and use case. Learning how actors use the technology by use cases helps you to better grasp how they communicate with the system.

Table 4-4 Connection between products and booking

Actors	Use case 1	Use case 2	How does the usage casework

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User	Search product as a user	Confirm Booking	This use case makes it possible for customers to browse and confirm reservations. Even, a non-registered user would be allowed to make a reservation. Once you have provided the necessary information, the booking will be verified. After the job is done, a notification is immediately sent to the user.
		Provide Feedback	In this usage case, the consumer uses the feature to offer feedback/comments to the company; and after a response has been submitted, a confirmation message will be sent to the customer.
Vendor	Add product as a vendor	Vendor Login	The usage case serves as an addition to the fleet database of the manufacturer. To trigger this use case, the vendor will need to log in.
	Edit product as a vendor		This use case is used by the vendor since each renewal of the item necessitates editing and modification of the data (insurance, road tax). It helps the corporation to maintain track of its fleet in an up-to-date manner.
	Delete product as a vendor		The vendor utilizes this usage case to completely exclude all of the internal product vehicles from the fleet log. In order to use this scenario, the vendor would need to log in.
	Register as		This usage case outlines the vendor's web registration and membership application practices. Registration requirements include

	a vendor		vendor information. If the registration is completed, the seller is notified and the login information is passed on automatically.
Administrator	See the booking details	Admin login	This use case is commonly used by the Admin to browse customer booking information.
	See all the feedbacks		In addition, the Admin will see the contact information that has been sent to the consumer through this use case.

4.5 Module design

Module detailed design

There are two kinds of authority users (vendors and customers) participating at the front desk. They participate in some modules of the front desk function respectively. The detailed design of the modules is described below, and the functions of three kinds of authorized users are described respectively. There is also one kind of authorized user (administrator) in the background. The detailed functions are described below.

1. User module

Provide inquiry details: Customers fill in the information on the inquiry box as customers.

Browse the query module: Browse all the products information, and also query the business product rental, car rental, Air conditioner rental, Audiovisual rental, Refrigerator rental, etc.

Feedback module: leave a message with an anonymous identity in the feedback part.

Figure 4.9 Customer module diagram

2. Vendor module

In addition to the customers above bRowe query module and message module, vendors also have the following functional modules.

Login module: The login framework is a gateway module that enables users to enter their usernames and passwords to log in. To log in to the framework, add this module to any module tab. Another resource for generating module tabs.

Registration modules: A register module aids in data entry for patients, so that: eases data entry & accuracy by matching the OpenMRS entry to the data source (usually paper files created at the point of care), ties easily back to individual patient records to connect registers to patient data and collects data elements to enable better supervision of treatment programs.

The vendor module diagram is given below :

Figure 4.10 Vendor module diagram

3. Administrator module

Product management module: the administrator modifies the product information and deletes the rental product information. Add maintenance information, including maintenance cost, maintenance days and maintenance reasons. Maintenance status

includes maintenance and OK. Maintenance means the product can't be rented yet. OK means the product can be rented after maintenance.

Message feedback management module: reply to members' complaints.

Order management module: according to the member's order, deposit and identity information, approve whether to rent the product.

Query module: On a daily basis administrator checks all the queries.

Statistics management module: generate income report according to a day or a month. The report includes the name of the vehicle, the lessee, the daily rental price, the estimated income, the lease start date and end date, and lists the type, time, reason, responsible party, the name of the vehicle, the lessee and the cost of the accident and violation.

The administrator module diagram is given below :

Figure 4.11 Administrator module diagram

4.6 Sequence Diagram

A sequence diagram represents item relationships in the order in which they occur. This figure highlights the various entities and groups which are present in the scenario, as well as the flow of messages between the different entities necessary to carry out the scenario's

intended functionality.

Sequence Diagram 1

Figure 4.12 Sequence Diagram 1

The Procedure of Admin sequence diagram flows as login to admin page by using the URL. The admin can interface first access to object's username and password to the login interface.

Sequence Diagram 2

Figure 4.13 Sequence Diagram 2

The procedure of the customer sequence diagram is the same as the admin sequence diagram. The customer will be the first to start the signup and then through sing in (login) once you login the customer account be registered and it will be stored on the database.

Sequence Diagram 3

Figure 4.14 Sequence Diagram 3

The employee Sequence diagram is shown in the above figure. The employee can be registered on the admin or home page. The employee will be the first to start the signup and then through sing in (login) once you login the customer account be registered and it will be stored on the database.

4.7 Design of the Database

a. Entity:

- Vendor_tab
- Product
- Party rentals
- Relocations
- Bookings
- Inquiry
- Feedbacks

b. Different properties of an entity

a. Vendor_tab

- First_Name_Sellers
- Last_Name_Sellers
- Sellers_User_Name
- Sellers_Password
- Sellers_Address
- Sellers_City
- Sellers_State
- Sellers_Pincode
- dealer_Credit_Card
- dealer_Mobile_No
- dealer_Telephone
- dealer_Email
- dealer_Another_Email
- dealer_Date
- dealer_Question
- Dealer_Answer

b. Product

- Vendor_Name
- producttype_
- availcity_
- Product_Name
- Starting_Time
- Ending_Time
- Renting
- Position
- Explanation
- picture_
- Product_Identity
- Vendor_User_Name

c. Party rentals

- name_
- date_
- requirement_
- Address
- Phone_Number
- Am_Pm
- Party_Mail

d. Bookings

- Booking_Name
- Booking_Email
- Booking_Phone_Number
- Booking_Number_Of_Pieces
- Product_Date
- Product_Hours
- Product_Minimum
- Product_Time
- Last_Date
- Product_Place
- productid_

e. Inquiry

- Specific_Request
- Request_Date
- name_
- phonenumber_
- e-mail_

f. Feedbacks

- FeedBackId_
- fname_
- femail_

- feedback_
- VUserName_

g. Relocation

- Name_
- Demand
- Date_And_Time
- Source_Address
- Destination_Address
- Phone_Number
- E-mail_

4.8 Data Dictionary

Table 4-5 Vendor Details Table

Serial Number	Name of the column	Limitations	References
I.	Given Name	No NULL	
II.	Family Name	No NULL	
III.	User_Name	Primary key	
IV.	Password_	No NULL	
V.	Address_	No NULL	
VI.	City_	No NULL	
VII.	State_	No NULL	
VIII.	Credit_Card_No_	No NULL	
IX.	Mobile_No_	No NULL	
X.	Tel_No_	Yes	
XI.	Email_Id_	No NULL	
XII.	Altenate_Email_	No NULL	
XIII.	Date_Of_Birth_	No NULL	
XIV.	Questions_	No NULL	
XV.	Answers_	No NULL	

Table 4-6 Products Table

Serial Number	Name of the column	Limitations	References
I.	Vendor_Name_	Primary key	
II.	Product_Type_	No NULL	

III.	Available_City_	No NULL	
IV.	Product_Name_	No NULL	
V.	Start_Date_	No NULL	
VI.	End_Date_	No NULL	
VII.	Rent_	No NULL	
VIII.	Status_	No NULL	
IX.	Description_	Yes	
X.	Picture_	No NULL	
XI.	Product_Id_	Foreign key	Products

Table 4-7 Party Rentals

Serial Number	Name of the column	Limitations	References
I.	Name_	Primary key	
II.	Date_	No NULL	
III.	Requirement_	No NULL	
IV.	Address_	No NULL	
V.	Phone_No_	No NULL	
VI.	AM_PM_	No NULL	
VII.	Party_Mail_	No NULL	

Table 4-8 Relocations

Serial Number	Name of the column	Limitations	References
I.	Name_	Primary key	
II.	Requirement_	No NULL	
III.	Date_	No NULL	
IV.	Source_Address_	No NULL	
V.	Destination_address_	No NULL	
VI.	Phone_N0_	No NULL	
VII.	Email_Id_	No NULL	

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Table 4-9 Bookings

Serial Number	Name of the column	Limitations	References
I.	Name_	Primary key	
II.	Requirement_	No NULL	
III.	Date_	No NULL	
IV.	Source_Address_	No NULL	
V.	Destination_address_	No NULL	
VI.	Phone_No_	No NULL	
VII.	Email_id_	No NULL	

Table 4-10 Enquiry

Serial Number	Column Name	Limitations	References
I.	Name_	Primary key	
II.	Requirement_	No NULL	
III.	Date_	No NULL	
IV.	Source_Address_	No NULL	
V.	Destination_Address_	No NULL	
VI.	Phone_No_	No NULL	
VII.	E-mail_	No NULL	

Table 4-11 Feedback

Serial Number	Name of the column	Limitations	References
I.	Name_	Primary key	
II.	E-mail id	No NULL	

Chapter 5 Implementation of Project

5.1 Implementation of vendor

a. Add product:

Figure 5-1 Add product

Details about the algorithm :

The procedure of the vendor is to add products/update products. In order to login to the vendor login interface; first, need to provide the User Name and Password to the login interface. Once login to the vendor page; we add products once it approves the product admin can moderate of product and then it will be approved.

Coding part :

```
publicpartialclassadd_product : System.Web.UI.Page
{
protectedvoid Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
{

}
protectedvoid btnadd_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
```

```
{  
  
int avail = int.Parse(lblavail.Text);  
if (avail == 1)  
{  
if (FileUpload1.PostedFile != null && FileUpload1.PostedFile.FileName !=  
"")  
{  
byte[] myimage = newbyte[FileUpload2.PostFile.ContentLength];  
HttpPostedFile Image = FileUpload2.PostFile;  
Image.InputStream.Read(myimage, 0,  
(int)FileUpload2.PostFile.ContentLength);  
SqlConnection cn =  
newSqlConnection(ConfigurationSettings.AppSettings["sree"]);
```

b. Delete product

Figure 5-2 Delete product

Details about the algorithm :

The procedure of the vendor is to delete the products. Once your Product will be delete the message will appear for confirmation of product deletion. Yes you want deletion to go through the delete button click on the delete button your product will be deleted

Coding part :

```
publicpartialclassdeleteproduct : System.Web.UI.Page
{

SqlConnection
cn=newSqlConnection(ConfigurationSettings.AppSettings["sree"]);
SqlDataAdapter da;
DataSet ds;
SqlCommandBuilder cmb;
DataTable dt;
DataRow row;
int I;
protectedvoid Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    cn.Open();
}
protectedvoid Button2_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
if (DropDownList1.SelectedIndex == 0)
    {
    }
if (DropDownList1.SelectedIndex == 1)
    {
string s;
        s = "delete from products where productid=" +
int.Parse(DropDownList2.SelectedItem.Text);
```

c. Registration

Figure 5-3 Registration

Details about the algorithm :

User registration: start the registration first you signup u already on account directly you log in otherwise signup fill the form and then submit this register will be stored on the database. Once you register go through sign-in page.

Coding part :

```
int avail = int.Parse(lblavail.Text);
if (avail == 1)
{
SqlConnection cn =
newSqlConnection(ConfigurationSettings.AppSettings["sree"]);
SqlCommand cmd = newSqlCommand();
```

```
cn.Open();
cmd.Connection = cn;
cmd.CommandType = CommandType.Text;
cmd.CommandText = "insert into vendortab values('" +
txtfname.Text + "','" + txtlname.Text + "','" + txtusername.Text + "','"
+ txtpswd.Text + "','" + txtaddress.Text + "','" + ddlcity.Text + "','"
+ txtstate.Text + "','" + txtpincode.Text + "','" + txtccno.Text + "','"
+ txtmobileno.Text + "','" + txttelno.Text + "','" + txtemail.Text +
 "','" + txtaltemail.Text + "','" + txtdate.Text + "','" +
ddlsecquestion.Text + "','" + txtsecanswer.Text + "')";
cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
cn.Close();
Session["vfname"] = txtfname.Text;
Session["vlname"] = txtlname.Text;
Session["vuname"] = txtusername.Text;
Session["vpwd"] = txtpswd.Text;
Session["vaddress"] = txtaddress.Text;
Session["vcity"] = ddlcity.Text;
Session["vstate"] = txtstate.Text;
Session["vpincode"] = txtpincode.Text;
Session["vcredit"] = txtccno.Text;
Session["vmobile"] = txtmobileno.Text;
Session["vtel"] = txttelno.Text;
Session["vemail"] = txtemail.Text;
Session["vaemail"] = txtaltemail.Text;
Session["vdate"] = txtdate.Text;
Session["vquestion"] = ddlsecquestion.Text;
Session["vanswer"] = txtsecanswer.Text;
Response.Redirect("successregister.aspx");
}
```

d. Forget password

Figure 5-4 Forgot password

Details about the algorithm :

Forgot password: Before login to the vendor login interface first need to provide the User Name and Password to the login interface. Then the system will read the user information from the database and match the password. If every information is correct then the user will be able to see the vendor interface; Otherwise, an error message will be displayed.

Coding part :

```
publicpartialclassforgotpassword : System.Web.UI.Page
{
    SqlConnection cn =
    newSqlConnection(ConfigurationSettings.AppSettings["sree"]);
    protectedvoid Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
    }
    protectedvoid btnsubmit1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
    {
        cn.Open();
        SqlCommand cmd = newSqlCommand("select count(*) from vendortab where
vuname='" + txtusername.Text + "' ", cn);
        int c = int.Parse(cmd.ExecuteScalar().ToString());
        if (c == 1)
        {
            SqlCommand cmd1 = newSqlCommand("select vquestion from vendortab where
vuname='" + txtusername.Text + "' ", cn);
            SqlDataReader dr = cmd1.ExecuteReader();
            while (dr.Read())
                txtsqn.Text = dr[0].ToString();
            lblsqn.Visible = true;
            txtsqn.Visible = true;
            lblsans.Visible = true;
            txtsans.Visible = true;
            lblpwd.Visible = false;
            txtpwd.Visible = false;
            //lblpassword.Visible = true;
            //txtpassword.Visible = true;
            //HyperLink1.Visible = true;
            lblmsg1.Visible =false ;
            btnsubmit2.Visible = true;
            btnsubmit1.Visible = false;
        }
    }
}
```

5.2 Implementation of Admin

a. Admin Login:

Figure 5-5 Admin Login

Details about the algorithm :

Admin login: admin login process will be shown on the above flowchart. Admin login interface first needs to provide the User Name and Password to the login interface. Once you enter the admin page you can change or update information that will be shown on the front page and stored on the database.

Coding part :

```
publicpartialclassadminlogin1 : System.Web.UI.Page
{
protectedvoid Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
{

}
protectedvoid Button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
```

```
if (txtadmin.Text == "admin"&& txtadminpwd.Text == "admin")
{
    Response.Redirect("adminhome1.aspx");
}
else
{
    lblmsg.Text = "Invalid Username or Password";
}
}
protectedvoid txtadmin_TextChanged(object sender, EventArgs e)
```

b. Forget Password :

Figure 5-6 Forget password

Details about the algorithm :

The procedure is almost the same as an admin login. Before login to the vendor login

interface first need to provide the User Name and Password to the login interface. Then the system will read the user information from the database and match the password. If all information is correct then the user will be able to see the vendor interface; If the condition is not met, an error message would be shown.

Coding part :

```
public partial class admin_forgot1 : System.Web.UI.Page
{
protected void Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
}
protected void btnsubmit2_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
if (txtadminname.Text == "admin" && txtkeyword.Text == "rental system")
{
lblmsg.Text = "";
lblpwd.Visible = true;
txtpwd.Visible = true;
txtpwd.Text = "erenthub";
}
else
{
lblmsg.Text = "incorrect admin name or keyword ";
}
}
}
```

5.3 Implementation of customer

a. Feedback:

Figure 5-7 Customer feedback

Details about the algorithm :

The customer feedback process will be shown on the above flowchart. Feedback will be stored on the admin page by the customer. The feedback is positive record the feedback. Otherwise, feedback is negative go through the admin manager will solve the negative feedback.

Coding part :

```
publicpartialclassfeedback : System.Web.UI.Page
{
protectedvoid Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
{

}
protectedvoid Button1_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{

SqlConnection cn =
newSqlConnection(ConfigurationSettings.AppSettings["sree"]);
SqlCommand cmd = newSqlCommand();
cn.Open();
cmd.Connection = cn;
cmd.CommandType = CommandType.Text;
cmd.CommandText = "insert into feedback(fname,femail,feedback)
values('" + txtfeedname.Text + "','" + txtfeedemail.Text + "','" +
txtfeedback.Text + "')";
cmd.ExecuteNonQuery();
cn.Close();
Session["fname"] = txtfeedname.Text;
Session["femail"] = txtfeedemail.Text;
Session["feedback"] = txtfeedback.Text;
Response.Redirect("feedbacksubmit.aspx");
}
}
```

b. Booking :

Figure 5-8 Booking

Details about the algorithm :

The user interfaces for the system while a customer enters the application for the first time, he must register; the next time he logs in, the user name and password will be compared to the user records in the database's users table, and the product will be booked.

Coding part :

```
public partial class booking : System.Web.UI.Page
{
    SqlConnection cn =
    new SqlConnection(ConfigurationSettings.AppSettings["sree"]);
    SqlCommand cmd;
```

```
protectedvoid Page_Load(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
}
protectedvoid btnclear_Click(object sender, EventArgs e)
{
    txtuname.Text="";
    txtumail.Text="";
    txtuphone.Text = "";
    txtnumber.Text="";
    txtpdate.Text="";

    ddlhours.Text="";
    ddlminutes.Text="";
    ddlam.Text="";
    txtldate.Text="";
    txtpaddress.Text="";
}
```

Chapter 6 Testing of the system

The diagram of the system testing is given below:

Figure 6-1 Testing of the system

6.1 Evaluation of devices

The component is the smallest program design instrument and the verification effort is focused on system screening. We have a white box computer scanning, and in certain modules, the measurements run parallel.

WRITH BOX SCREENING

This screening method guarantees that – at least where all separate paths are determined all logical conclusions about their true and wrong implications have been taken. - Both loops were extended both in their operational limits and beyond their limits.

In order to verify their authenticity, all internal information structures have been placed to the test.

In order to keep to the White Box search principle, we checked any form separately. All queries are examined in order to assess their feasibility and all loops are carried out within their borders, which we have independently created to ensure the correct flow of knowledge.

A CONDITIONAL BASIS SCREENING.

Each parameter was checked for true and false components at this point of research. And all the classes that resulted were investigated in order to guarantee that a path is mapped to detect potential glitches by a particular problem.

INFORMATION FLOW TESTING

This screening approach utilizes variables that select the direction of the software depending on the area of definition. This method of research was used only when certain variables of the neighborhood were listed. The chain-definition approach was used in this form of research. This was especially helpful in embedded sentences.

LOOP TESTING Processing is the fifth stage of the testing process.

Both loops are assessed to their full limits through this assessment tool. The next technique has been used for both lapses: all lapses have been checked only over and just beyond their thresholds.

At least once, several loops have been skipped.

Start by the various inner loopholes and function outwards when searching for embedded loopholes.

With the help of a related loophole, the values of dependent loopholes are determined in concatenated loops.

Disorganized loopholes have been reorganized and analyzed as above in embedded loops or concatenated loopholes.

The development team checked each machine carefully on its own.

6.2 Examples of Test Cases:

Verification of registration part is given below :

Table 6-1 Verification of registration

registration	High (H) priority
Verification of registration is the aim of this test.	
Test Description: “The user fills in the appropriate fields and clicks the log icon,” the client software communicates with the server, the server communicates with the Database, Updates the Database and sends the user output.	
Yes, the prerequisites have been confirmed.	
IIS and the database server must all be operational throughout the test, and the database must be available. A suitable table should be included, and It is necessary to establish a link between the server and client applications.	
Pre-Conditions/Setup for the Test: It is essential for the IIS server to be operational. You must fill out all of the necessary fields.	
Taking Action	Results to be Expected
To access the application, the customer must first register.	The relevant Pages are shown.
Yes, the exam was passed.	Yes, the conditions are met. No, you did not fail.
Issues and problems: None.	
Observations: Registration was completed successfully.	

Authentication part is given below :

Table 6-2 Authentication

Second test event: Authentication is being confirmed.	High (H) priority
Verification of Authentication is the aim of this test.	
Description of the assessment: “The customer types his or her username and password and clicks the submit button,” the software application communicates with a server, the server communicates with the database, the database verifies the user’s identity, and the database sends the result as a legitimate person.	
Yes, the prerequisites have been confirmed.	
IIS and the DataBase server must be operational throughout the test, and the database must be available. A suitable table should be included, and It is necessary to establish a link between the server and client applications.	
Pre-Conditions/Setup for the Test: Both the IIS and the DataBase servers should be up and working. You can fill out the UserName and Password sections.	
Expected Outcomes of Actions	The customer enters his or her informationand
The user clicks the send icon.	“Valid User” is a phrase that may be used to describe someone that has The Main Menu would be shown.
Yeah, the exam was passed. Yeah, the requirements are met. No, you did not fail.	
Issues/Problems: None	
Notes: User verification was completed successfully.	

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Add product parts given below :

Table 6-3 Add products

Third test event: Add products		High (H) priority
The aim of this test is to see how well you can add items to your cart.		
“The user enters the appropriate fields and clicks the Additem icon,” the client software communicates with the server, the server communicates with the database, the database is updated, and the user receives the output.		
Yes, the prerequisites have been confirmed.		
IIS and the database server must all be operational throughout the test, and the database must be available. A suitable table should be included, and It is necessary to establish a link between the server and client applications.		
Pre-Conditions/Setup for the Test: It is essential for the IIS server to be operational. You must fill out all of the necessary fields.		
Taking Action		Results to be Expected
The user fills in the required information and then presses the “Add” icon.		The relevant Pages are shown.
Yeah, the exam was passed.		Yes, the conditions are met. No, you did not fail.
Issues and problems: None.		
The product was successfully inserted, according to the notes.		

Delete product part is given below :

Table 6-4 delete products

Fourth test event: delete products		High (H) priority
The aim of this test is to see whether the substance can be deleted.		
“The user selects the appropriate fields and hits the delete button,” the client software communicates with the server, the server communicates with the database, the database is updated, and the user receives the output.		
Yes, the prerequisites have been confirmed.		
IIS and the database server must all be operational throughout the test, and the database must be available. A suitable table should be included, and It is necessary to establish a link between the server and client applications.		
Pre-Conditions/Setup for the Test: It is essential for the IIS server to be operational. You must fill out all of the necessary fields.		
Taking Action		Results to be Expected
The consumer will pick a product and then press uninstall,		bring up the relevant pages.
Yeah, the exam was passed. Yes, the conditions are met. No, you did not fail.		
Issues/Problems: None		
Notes: The products have been successfully deleted.		

Inserting part is given below :

Table 6-5 Insert

First test event: Insert	High (H) priority
The aim of this test is to see how well you can insert requests.	
“The user enters the appropriate fields and hits the Submit button,” says the test description. “The software application contacts the server, the server contacts the database, the database changes, and the result is sent to the customer,” says the test description.	
Yes, the prerequisites have been confirmed.	
Yes, the prerequisites have been confirmed. IIS and the database server must all be operational throughout the test, and the database must be available. A suitable table should be included, and It is necessary to establish a link between the server and client applications.	
Pre-Conditions/Setup for the Test: It is essential for the IIS server to be operational. You must fill out all of the necessary fields.	
Taking Action	Results to be Expected
The consumer will choose a product and submit an inquiry	display the relevant pages
Yeah, the exam was passed. Yes, the conditions are met. No, you did not fail.	
Issues and problems: None.	
Notes: The request has been submitted successfully.	

6.3 Summary :

The testing part is one of the most important parts among all the parts to build a complete project. There is a total of five testing activities. Five test cases have been executed here.

The five test cases are: Registration, Authentication, Add products, Delete products, and Inset. All the events were under high priority. After testing all the test cases, I have found that it has met all the conditions. All the test cases have been passed and there are no failures in any test case. No issues and problems have been found in any test case. After completing the testing process, I can determine that this software can be handed over to the buyer, or I can use this software for the business purpose.

Chapter 7 Screens Performance

7.1 Output screens

The Front Page

Figure 7-1 Home Page

This is the homepage. In this page customers will be able to see all the features. Customers can search the product from here. He can book and also rent any product from here. This interface is actually the parent interface among all the pages. Because from this page vendor and customers will know what to do and how to do.

Vendor Home screen

Figure 7-2 Home Page of the Vendor

Every single one of the photographs in this montage above shows the vendor. Additional information about the vendor management section is given below :

- To accept vendors online, the business owner simply clicks on the Expand button and allows the application to process.
- By the administrator, it is possible to edit all vendor details.
- Merchants may be inserted or omitted from the administration panel.
- There are no fees levied on vendors. Also, this option will be added in the near future.
- Reduce the payments to vendors and sales
- Track and maintain vendor relationships (what data is collected about them when they sign up)
- You should set it up such that all vendors must be registered and pre-approved to get their goods featured on your site (or auto-approve)
- The vendors are able to incorporate or exclude products or change at will.
- The vendor is allowed to alter his own details on the vendor registration form.

Home Page of the Admin

Figure 7-3 Home Page of the Admin

Basically, this part is illustrating the admin details. After providing the username and password, the admin can enter into the admin homepage. On the homepage, the admin can see all the feedbacks, orders, inquiries, etc. Admin manages the database. Admin can edit any information from the database. If the admin forgets his own password, he can retrieve the password at any time. After completing all the tasks, he can just simply sign out from the system.

7.2 Summary :

This chapter shows all the output screens of the web application. In the application, all the features are for the vendor, customer and admin. The design is simple and user-friendly. There are no complicated options in the whole system. Users can easily login_ and logout_. Customers can easily book or rent any products from the website. Customers can also be able to cancel their orders at any time. All the features which have been implemented for the vendor are also easy. The vendor doesn't need to ask the admin again and again to edit, delete or add some items or any information.

Conclusions

After the coding and paper writing in recent months, the graduation project will come to an end. In the graduation design of the “Design and implementation of online rental system” based on Web, I made use of the basic knowledge of Web application I learned before, referred to relevant books, and went through constant testing and adjustment. Finally, a prototype. Since this project covers a relatively comprehensive area, from the initial data inquiry to the final step-by-step practice, I have gained a deeper understanding of software development and accumulated a lot of theoretical knowledge. From demand analysis, feasibility analysis, and later Java environment configuration, code writing, and debugging, I, as a user, have a certain knowledge of web application specifications and of the software world. In this, the database connection debugging is very troublesome, but solved is also an exciting thing.

This graduation project also makes me realize that in this era of continuous development of different software, our life has been inseparable from the updated technology. And the network makes our life more and more convenient, more and more labor-saving and efficient. Especially in terms of food, clothing, housing, and transportation, this is indispensable for everyone. This online ordering undoubtedly has a very important impact on our life. Moreover, once it is applied, it will reduce the workload of going to the shopping mall physically, spending a lot of money to buy any new product, etc. Only by solving the fundamental problems can we make a qualitative leap forward.

This graduation project, let me have consolidation and promotion of the previous knowledge. And this design let me realize that only good planning, such as requirements analysis and the outline of the overall design, only a clear analysis of them, the program can go on. If the overall design is not scientific, it will lead to mistakes in the detailed design, unclear goals, and even lost direction. Due to the limited technical level and time, there are still some deficiencies in the design, but the experience of this graduation project will exert an important influence and significance on my future study and work.

Renovations in the Future

Auto smartphone updates for customers, as well as provider processes, will be included in the future. If a customer places an order, notifications will be sent to the client's cell phone almost immediately. Similarly, whenever a supplier registers on our website, his or her exclusive username and password will be sent to his or her mobile device. Any product alerts will be sent to his cell phone as well. All fresh discounts or rewards can also be sent to the vendors' cell phones.

We currently retain provider, individual contact via e-mail id; but, in the future, we will implement it via mobile signals, submitting all customers' schedules as well as personal details to the supplier's mobile as soon as possible. We've since expanded our platform to include a large number of towns, as well as a much larger number of cities. We'll also have automated e-mail communication between the provider and the administrator.

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